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Seeing, thinking, sharing, sensing small data.

A participatory framework to connect citizens' experiences with urban governance

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This paper proposes a methodological framework for integrating *small data* into participatory approaches to urban governance. It conceptualises four interrelated practices – *seeing with*, *thinking through*, *sharing through*, and *sensing small data* – to articulate how data can be mobilised to bridge lived urban experience with institutional knowledge. The framework explores how locally generated, experientially grounded, and socially mediated forms of data can complement large-scale datasets by embedding observation, interpretation, co-creation, and embodied participation within the everyday life. Developed and tested through participatory workshops in [omitted for blind review] the research argue how small data on urban waste management operates as a relational and reflective medium that enables citizens to express situated perspectives and engage in collective sense-making. Initial findings and reflections on overall practices underscore the potential of participatory practices to incentivise small data to reveal the multilevel dynamics of urban systems and foster more inclusive, and context-sensitive forms of governance

CCS CONCEPTS • Human-centered computing → Human computer interaction (HCI) → Interaction design → Participatory design • Human-centered computing → Visualization → Visualization design and evaluation methods Information systems → Information systems applications → Spatial-temporal systems → Urban computing

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1 INTRODUCTION

Data has become a primary medium through which contemporary cities are managed and understood. Dominant approaches in urban governance rely on large-scale sensing and statistical infrastructures that prioritise prediction and efficiency, overlooking the lived experiences, tacit knowledge, and cultural practices shaping urban life. This paper argues

that small data –data generated through situated experiences – complements large datasets in urban governance by grounding urban inquiry in everyday experience.

The discussion unfolds in three parts. First, a literature review traces how small data has been conceptualised across research and design traditions, highlighting its role as both lived practice and cultural material, and its value in participatory contexts, as a medium for dialogue and reflection. Building on this, the paper proposes four interrelated methodological practices – *seeing with, thinking through, sharing through, and sensing small data* – conceived as dialogical processes through which data acquires meaning from cultural and social life.

The proposed framework emerges from the [omitted for blind review] project, an [omitted for blind review] research initiative exploring the role of digital twins and data science in the urban context of [omitted for blind review], [omitted for blind review], and was developed through a series of participatory activities involving citizens that informed and shaped its formulation. Within the main purpose of the project, which concentrates on predictive analytics and large-scale infrastructures, our contribution focuses on participatory methods to reframe data as a medium for connecting citizens’ collective experiences with urban governance. A case study in [omitted for blind review], centred on waste management as a concrete field for exploring how small data can reveal the interconnections between infrastructures, behaviours, and cultural practices shaping everyday urban life. The topic provided the occasion to connect municipal datasets to everyday practices through workshops with citizens and students, fostering dialogue and collaborative interpretation.

The paper concludes by highlighting key insights: the value of prototyping and mapping as participatory tools, the role of enabling technologies in empowering small-scale data practices, and the need to sustain dialogue between citizens, institutions, and urban governance.

2 SMALL DATA AS SITUATED MEANING

The rise of big data brought claims that large-scale datasets could revolutionise knowledge production across domains such as healthcare, commerce, and urban governance. While these systems reveal powerful correlations [5], they have been criticised for reducing complex lived experience to abstract, standardised categories [33, 2]. In response to this abstraction, scholars have turned their attention to small data as a way to ground data practices in lived, contextual realities.

Rather than being defined by scale, small data is understood through its proximity to experience and its capacity to reflect everyday life. The concept of “small data, where $n = me$ ” captures how the traces generated through daily routines can yield valuable insight precisely because they remain close to individual contexts [10]. In health research, this orientation supports adaptive feedback processes that align interventions with personal trajectories rather than universal population models [14]. Similarly, in urban and social contexts, small data exposes and challenges the blind spots of data-intensive infrastructures, particularly within marginalised or resource-constrained communities [13]. Through these perspectives, specificity and responsiveness emerge as methodological principles that keep data connected to the realities it represents.

At a conceptual level, small data has been framed as a mode of theorising that draws attention to the cultural and institutional conditions shaping data production [21]. This perspective positions small data as both an analytical and reflexive means of questioning how knowledge is constructed and circulated. When carefully assembled, small datasets can illuminate complex interdependencies, such as those within ecological systems, that remain invisible to large-scale, aggregated models [30]. This orientation toward context and reflexivity resonates with the notion of *thick data*, which extends ethnographic traditions to emphasise the meaning, motivation, and affect underpinning data practices [34]. Grounded in Geertz’s concept of *thick description*, thick data foregrounds interpretation as a central element in understanding human activity [12]. Building on this interpretive stance, data work can be understood as a continuous

process of sensemaking, through which records acquire significance within specific cultural and institutional settings [23]. Attention to the sensory and material dimensions of experience further enriches this understanding, situating data within the embodied and affective textures of everyday life [25].

The value of small data becomes more tangible in self-tracking practices, where metrics are interpreted and woven into everyday routines. These embodied engagements turn data into a medium for reflection on bodies, habits, and environments [18, 19], while discourses of optimisation, well-being, and self-care shape how individuals make sense of these records [29]. In this context, the act of tracking exposes the infrastructural assumptions and power relations that organise systems of measurement [23]. These practices blur the boundaries between quantitative and qualitative registers of knowing. Numerical indicators are frequently combined with notes, emotions, and contextual reflections, producing hybrid records that merge measurement with narrative [28]. The significance of small data thus lies not in the numbers themselves but in how they are situated, appropriated, and reinterpreted within everyday life. Beyond tracking, small data extends into personal archiving, where diaries, logs, and curated collections function as artefacts of both individual and collective memory, demonstrating that data's value resides in the social and cultural practices that sustain it [1].

Taken together, these perspectives point to an epistemology in which quantitative records and qualitative interpretation are intertwined. The value of data lies not in its scale but in its capacity to situate knowledge within lived experience. Whether through the immediacy of personal traces, the narrative depth of ethnographic accounts, or the careful curation of small datasets, small data approaches demonstrate how meaning emerges from context and interpretation. In the urban domain, this orientation towards small data converges with emerging efforts to recontextualise data practices, linking global analytical frameworks with the situated realities of everyday urban life [15]. Systematic reviews of big-data research emphasise the need to integrate spatial and social dimensions for addressing the complex interrelations that define contemporary cities [9]. Building on this trajectory, recent work in urban informatics demonstrates how technological and educational innovation can support more context-sensitive approaches to urban analysis and planning [17]. Yet, despite these developments, most research continues to operate at infrastructural and institutional scales, where data remains abstracted from the lived experiences and social relations through which it acquires meaning. What remains underdeveloped is a sustained understanding of how data practices might embed participatory and experiential dimensions – recognising citizens not only as data sources but as contributors to the production and interpretation of urban knowledge.

Within this context, the project unfolds through the following research question: how might small data practices be mobilised to foster collective forms of knowledge-making and reconfigure the relationship between data, citizenship, and urban governance?

3 CONNECTING SMALL DATA TO LARGE-SCALE MODELS THROUGH PARTICIPATORY PRACTICES

Building on the question of how small data practices might reconfigure the relationship between data, knowledge, and urban governance, participation emerges as a central dimension. While small data foregrounds proximity, experience, and reflexivity, participatory approaches offer the social and institutional conditions through which these qualities can operate at the urban scale.

Integrating small data and participatory design thus provides a means of linking embodied experience to collective knowledge production and decision-making. Although small data has often been associated with self-tracking and individual reflection, its potential extends far beyond the personal. Scholars in critical data studies argue that small and big data are not opposing paradigms but complementary forms of knowledge: the fine-grained detail of small data gives meaning to large-scale models, while aggregated datasets situate local insights within broader systems of understanding

[6]. Even in technological and organisational domains, small data increasingly functions as an interpretive layer, an epistemic interface that renders large-scale information actionable and contextually meaningful [19].

In design research, this relational understanding translates into practices where data acts as a catalyst for dialogue rather than a tool for measurement. Designing partial, situated, and co-produced datasets becomes a shared site of inquiry [27]. The concept of Participatory Data Design captures processes in which stakeholders collectively determine what counts as data, how it is collected, and how it is interpreted [16]. Such approaches give rise to *data publics*: temporary arenas of deliberation and speculation in which data serves as a medium for shared meaning-making [8]. Within these spaces, collaboratively visualised small datasets foster cross-disciplinary interpretation, transforming information into material for collective discussion and critique [4].

Recent experiments in urban and spatial research have extended these ideas to collective contexts. Technology plays a central role in this evolution, not simply as a tool for data capture but as a mediating interface that shapes how data is produced, visualised, and interpreted [11]. Through digital platforms, mobile applications, and visual tools, data becomes both a record of lived experience and a prompt for dialogue between citizens, researchers, and institutions [7, 31]. The Urban Belonging project illustrates this orientation through a co-designed photovoice app that enabled participants to annotate places of belonging and exclusion, prioritising lived experience over fixed spatial categories and transforming personal images into collective narratives that informed planning debates [3, 20]. The Walking and Talking method expanded this logic by combining spatial movement with the collection of images, sounds, and tags, producing multimodal traces later revisited in group sessions where participants co-constructed their meaning and reframed them as shared cultural resources [26].

Despite these contributions, current research and practice still lack a clear articulation of how small data can be mobilised within participatory urban processes to inform decision-making and collective transformation. What remains underexplored is how small data can move beyond individual or experimental applications to become a structured means of participation that informs governance. Clarifying how and why small data can be activated in participatory contexts is crucial to understanding its potential to link lived experience with processes of urban planning, policy, and design.

4 INTEGRATING SMALL DATA INTO PARTICIPATORY URBAN CONTEXTS: THE CASE STUDY OF [OMITTED FOR BLIND REVIEW]

This contribution advances the integration of small data into participatory urban governance by proposing a methodological framework. The framework illustrates how small data can support civic engagement and collective sensemaking across the stages of the urban process, from the generation of situated insights to their transformation into shared knowledge and action. The chapter first introduces the context from which the framework emerged, describing the participatory workshops conducted in [omitted for blind review], within the [omitted for blind review]. It then presents the four methodological practices that define the proposed framework.

4.1 Waste as Situated Data

Two workshops enabled sustained engagement with local contexts and direct collaboration with the Municipality of [omitted for blind review]. The aim was to examine how citizen participation and local data practices could foster new forms of communication and collaboration between residents and governance actors. This setting offered the opportunity to investigate small data through situated encounters with urban phenomena and everyday data practices, positioning participation as a mode of inquiry grounded in local experience.

Urban waste management was identified as a particularly generative field through which to explore small data, because waste functions as infrastructure, routine, and cultural artefact simultaneously, making it an ideal lens for examining how data reveals the entanglement of material flows, social values, and behaviours in urban life. Scholars have shown how discarded matter exposes these interdependencies, from the “fatbergs” clogging London’s sewers as material ecologies of disposal [30], to Trash Track, which traced the global circulation of refuse through sensor-based mapping [22].

The first workshop, involving student groups, focused on prototyping data-scraping tools to document waste practices. The second, engaging citizens, expanded these prototypes into participatory activities such as mapping routines, co-designing indicators, and collectively interpreting visualisations. These encounters revealed how institutional datasets, while extensive, often overlook the tacit, embodied, and cultural dimensions of waste infrastructures. By foregrounding these situated forms of knowledge, small data became a shared medium for inquiry, enabling participants to challenge established categories and explore alternative ways of understanding and governing urban systems.

4.2 The Framework: Four Methodological Practices

The framework unfolds four methodological practices to operate within urban contexts by integrating small data and participatory design. The framework links embodied experience to collective knowledge production and decision-making, defining small data as locally generated, experientially grounded, and socially mediated information emerging from everyday practices of observation and engagement.

This form of knowledge is produced in proximity to lived experience, where meaning arises through interaction and situated reflection. In participatory settings, small data enables citizens to interpret their environments and contribute to shared processes of understanding and decision-making. Within urban governance, it complements large-scale analytical systems by providing the contextual depth needed to connect institutional models with lived realities, fostering inquiry grounded in situated understanding rather than abstraction.

Grounded in participatory activities, the framework articulates four methodological practices – *seeing with*, *thinking through*, *sharing through*, and *sensing small data* – which describe how small data operates within participatory processes, specifying when it becomes active and what purposes it serves, Figure 1. Rather than forming a linear sequence, these practices constitute an interconnected system of inquiry linking data generation to interpretation, communication, and embodied engagement. Each one defines a distinct mode to engage citizens with small data to observe their surroundings, construct shared meaning, and contribute to collective reflection and action.

Seeing with small data captures the capacity to access urban phenomena from situated perspectives, revealing the material, social, and environmental dynamics that are often overlooked by institutional forms of observation. Through practices of recording and capturing small data, citizens engage with the city as active observers, generating traces that ground inquiry in lived contexts and make local issues visible.

Thinking through small data articulates the interpretive function of small data, showing how, once organised and visualised, it becomes a basis for collective reflection and analysis. This process enables communities and public actors to connect individual experiences with broader urban patterns and to negotiate shared understandings of the city.

Sharing through small data highlights its communicative and dialogical dimension, demonstrating how participatory mapping and co-design practices transform dispersed observations into shared artefacts. These artefacts foster dialogue, co-creation, and mutual learning among citizens, researchers, and institutions.

Sensing small data emphasises its embodied and experienced dimension, showing how gestures, movements, and sensory engagements integrate data into the corporeal and material realities of urban life. Through this process, knowledge is reunited with lived experience, reinforcing the connection between participation, perception, and urban awareness.

Figure 2: Visual representation of the iterative methodological framework showing the four interconnected practices – Seeing, Thinking, Sharing, and Sensing. The diagram organises the framework across three dimensions: methodological practices, what data emerged, and how participation unfolds

4.3 Seeing with small data: situated access

How can the collection of small data enable more situated and participatory engagements with urban phenomena? The first methodological practice, *seeing with small data*, addresses this question by conceptualising observation and data collection as situated acts of inquiry, processes through which participants encounter and interpret the city from within its lived, material, and social conditions. In this perspective, seeing is not a passive act of documentation but an epistemic and participatory operation that entails attentiveness, relationality, and reflexivity. It invites citizens to observe the urban environment through alternative and more granular points of view, to recognise patterns and rhythms that are typically rendered invisible, and to engage with the infrastructures and behaviours that shape everyday urban life.

The practice was elaborated through the two participatory workshops. The first, organised with multidisciplinary students at the [omitted for blind review], focused on prototyping DIY sensing devices to enable citizen-led observation of waste practices. Preliminary discussions with municipal data officers had revealed the limits of existing datasets, which, while extensive, remained detached from the lived, sensory, and temporal dimensions of waste management, such as overflow conditions, accessibility constraints, or habitual routines. Students were therefore invited to address these data absences by designing experimental toolkits capable of capturing and representing forms of small data that could complement official records while enabling citizens to develop a closer and more situated access to the urban phenomena.

The resulting devices, built with low-cost sensors and cameras, were conceived as mediating artefacts rather than as neutral instruments of measurement. By converting environmental data into real-time visualisations, such as thermal mapping, edge rendering, or algorithmic overlays, the prototypes allowed participants to view waste as a dynamic and relational phenomenon, Figure 2.

Figure 2: Urban scraping prototypes developed during the first workshop. From left to right: DIY prototype displaying real-time thermal mapping; examples of algorithmic overlays for object detection and edge rendering; students showing the assembled hardware components of the prototype, integrating low-cost sensors and camera modules.

The second workshop, [omitted for blind review], held in [omitted for blind review], during the [omitted for blind review], expanded this exploration by engaging citizens in collective data walks across different neighbourhoods. Equipped with the toolkits, participants collected small data using sensor-based imaging and visual documentation to record eco-points, circulation routes, and informal accumulation sites, Figure 3. The gathered data, which included temperature variations, spatial constraints, and overflow patterns, revealed fine-grained details of how waste infrastructures function within the rhythms of everyday urban life. The walks transformed data collection into an exploratory and relational process, enabling participants to observe aspects of the urban environment that conventional monitoring systems rarely capture.

The toolkits revealed micro-level dynamics, such as localised inefficiencies, temporal fluctuations, and spatial asymmetries, that remain inaccessible through aggregated or large-scale data. The small data collected through this process offered a dual perspective. For citizens, it offered an opportunity to access and interpret the city's material and infrastructural realities from a local perspective. For institutional actors, it provided an alternative perspective through which to perceive the subtle dynamics that escape large-scale monitoring systems, offering new insights into urban complexity and responding to it.

Figure 3: Citizens using DIY sensing toolkits during the [omitted for blind review] workshop in [omitted for blind review].

4.4 Thinking through small data: collective interpretation

Thinking through small data proposes a methodological practice in which data becomes a medium for collective interpretation and critical reflection. It shifts the focus from collection to comprehension, exploring how small data can generate shared insights once they are revisited, visualised, and discussed with those who contributed to their production. In this perspective, data are not conceived as fixed representations but as evolving artefacts that acquire meaning through interpretation, dialogue, and their relation to lived experience.

The data produced in the previous phase were visualised and discussed with citizens in a dedicated session during the workshop. They were invited to revisit the material previously collected and to reflect on how each dataset had been produced within specific spatial and temporal conditions. By examining the images together with their corresponding data structures, participants recalled the circumstances of collection, discussed why some results emerged, and related them to the context of their generation, Figure 4.

Figure 4: Interfaces used with citizens to analyse and review the data collected by the DIY sensing prototypes during the data walks. The visualisations combine images, sensor readings, and algorithmic renderings into multiple views that enable participants to explore, compare, and interpret the small data collected.

These discussions focused on the urban sites explored during the collective walks, using the small data as a basis for dialogue and reflection. Participants revisited the places they had encountered, interpreting recorded traces through their own observations and experiences. This process fostered collective imagination, inviting them to envision alternatives, speculate on improvements, and rethink how urban spaces might perform differently. By re-examining the information in context, *thinking through small data*, transformed the act of interpretation into a process of dialogue and contextualisation, linking sensor-based traces to lived experiences and generating situated understandings of the urban environment.

4.5 Sharing Through Small Data: Dialogue Co-creation

To extend the previous phase and transform individual experiences into a discussion where collective meaning could emerge, small data was collected through mapping practices that made everyday journeys to recycling points and bins visible. Individual maps were then assembled into a collective installation designed to be seen and discussed, fostering dialogue and reflection among participants on their daily habits.

The mapping activity invited participants to reconstruct their own waste-disposal routines using Google Maps to trace their routes, which were then printed and annotated with materials such as coloured stickers, strings, pins, and handwritten notes. These tangible elements enabled participants to embed contextual information—such as household size, frequency and time of disposal, means of transport, and related daily activities—into their maps, transforming abstract data into personal and situated narratives, Figure 5.

Figure 5: On the left, citizens engaging with the collective mapping installation, creating and discussing maps together; on the right, examples of annotated maps showing routes, disposal frequency, and contextual details used to visualise and compare everyday waste practices.

Through this process, the maps evolved from descriptive records into reflective artefacts that captured both spatial and experiential dimensions of urban life. The material interaction encouraged participants to reinterpret their own actions, compare routines, and discuss the social and infrastructural factors shaping their practices. When assembled collectively, the maps revealed shared patterns and differences, providing a visual ground for identifying challenges and imagining improvements in accessibility, service design, and sustainability.

By materialising lived experiences into visual artefacts, *sharing through small data* acted as a boundary practice that mediated dialogue, co-creation, and collective reflection. The process enabled participants to externalise and compare their experiences, fostering shared awareness and collaborative interpretation. Through these exchanges, small data became not only a record of individual practices but a catalyst for participatory learning and the co-production of situated urban knowledge.

4.6 Sensing Small Data: Embodied Experience

Building on the co-creative nature of the previous phase, *sensing small data* introduces an embodied perspective, extending participation from producing shared artefacts to engaging with lived experiences of the phenomenon itself. This practice considers the body as a site of perception and situated knowledge, showing how gesture and sensory interaction can reveal aspects of urban life that remain hidden to abstract or representational forms of data.

The activity used a gesture-tracking installation in which participants were invited to perform the act of disposing of waste into a bin, Figure 6. The system recorded each gesture and its duration while projecting a real-time visualisation that responded to movements. This immediate feedback created a reciprocal relationship between action and perception, allowing participants to witness their gestures unfolding and to become aware of the physical and spatial negotiation within an everyday act rarely examined. The installation thus transformed ordinary behaviour into a moment of experiential reflection, revealing the interplay between body, material conditions, and infrastructural design.

Figure 5: Gesture-tracking installation exploring the embodied dimension of waste disposal. On the left, a participant performs the act of throwing waste while the system visualises the gesture in real time; on the right, the interface displays recorded movements used for reflection and discussion during the activity.

Participants then reviewed their recordings and annotated reflections on sensation, posture, and context, reconnecting recorded movement with lived conditions. These reflections exposed the corporeal and affective dimensions of waste practices, showing how bodily engagement shapes accessibility, effort, and adaptation in relation to urban systems. Sensing small data expands participatory inquiry to the sensory and embodied domains, transforming physical experience into a source of situated knowledge. And reinforcing the framework’s co-creative scope through the interplay of collective meaning-making and individual-lived experience.

5 CONCLUSION AND PRELIMINARY ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS

The four methodological practices developed in this study – *seeing with*, *thinking through*, *sharing through*, and *sensing small data* – illustrate how participatory approaches can reconnect data production with lived urban experience. Together, they form a framework that integrates observation, interpretation, communication, and embodiment into a unified process of participatory sense-making. Through these practices, small data becomes a medium for citizens to explore, understand, and reimagine their relationship with urban infrastructures and governance.

Applying the framework to waste management in [omitted for blind review] revealed its capacity to generate multiple layers of insight. It enabled citizens to engage with urban phenomena from situated perspectives, revealing the material, behavioural, and cultural dynamics often absent from institutional datasets. Finally, the process demonstrated the epistemic

value of participation itself, positioning citizens as interpreters, co-creators, and embodied participants in the collective understanding of the city rather than as passive data sources.

A preliminary thematic analysis of the small dataset collected through this framework highlights the convergence of accessibility, spatial configuration, and everyday mobility in shaping waste-related practices. Participants' reflections revealed a number of interconnected issues, including the size and placement of collection bins, the limited availability of safe pedestrian crossings, and the absence of continuous walkable routes connecting residential areas to waste points. These observations revealed the direct influence of urban planning and micro-mobility conditions on citizens' ability to perform sustainable disposal practices. Other comments addressed the physical and ergonomic challenges of interacting with infrastructures, such as the weight and minimum capacity of municipal waste bags, which were often perceived as excessive for small households, to the difficulty of handling containers with narrow openings or unclear labelling. Participants also expressed a broader concern for the city's recycling culture, noting that infrastructure alone cannot ensure sustainability without greater civic awareness and shared responsibility.

These findings demonstrate the diagnostic potential of small data in revealing how infrastructural design, spatial organisation, and everyday behaviour are entangled within urban systems. By enabling participants to generate, visualise, and interpret their own data, the framework turns local experiences into shared understanding. In this way, small data serve as mediators between individual perception and collective governance, fostering more context-sensitive and participatory forms of urban knowledge production.

6 LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

The project is still ongoing, and the results presented in this paper are preliminary. The workshops have recently been completed, and the collected material is now under analysis. The findings discussed here should therefore be regarded as early insights rather than final outcomes. While the framework demonstrates how small data can support participatory urban inquiry, the limited number of participants and the short duration of the activities reduced the possibility of assessing long-term effects on governance or citizen practices. Future work should focus on extended collaborations to examine how small-data practices can evolve and contribute to lasting institutional change.

The next step involves presenting the results to the municipality, which played a role in identifying the initial problems and concerns discussed during the design of the activities. This stage aims to explore how the exchange can become more productive and how the findings can inform ongoing urban decision-making. Strengthening this relationship will be essential for embedding participatory data practices into policy design and governance processes. The role of municipal actors is expected to evolve from defining areas of inquiry to contributing to the interpretation and application of results, using small-data insights to improve public services and promote more responsive forms of governance.

Further applications in areas such as mobility, energy, and public space could demonstrate the broader potential of small data to connect everyday experiences with systemic urban transformations.

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